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Unveiling Landscape-Level Drivers of Freshwater Biodiversity Dynamics

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ABSTRACT

Human activities severely impact biodiversity, particularly in freshwater lakes. These habitats provide critical ecosystem services and, at the same time, suffer from river inflow, agricultural runoff, and urban discharge. DNA-based techniques are preferred for monitoring biodiversity due to their effectiveness. However, pinpointing the causes of biodiversity decline across landscapes poses challenges due to the complex interactions between biodiversity and environmental drivers. In this study, we used an explainable multimodal machine learning approach that can integrate different types of data, such as biological, chemical, and physical data, to discover potential causes of biodiversity dynamics. This is done by identifying relationships between environmental drivers—plant protection products, physico-chemical parameters and typology- and community biodiversity changes in 52 lake ecosystems. By analyzing benthic and pelagic lake communities, we found significant correlations between biodiversity and environmental drivers, such as plant protection products. Furthermore, our analysis allowed us to identify factors within these drivers responsible for biodiversity dynamics. Specifically, insecticides and fungicides were identified as the most important factors, followed by 43 physico-chemical factors, including many heavy metals. Our holistic, data-driven approach provides insights into large-scale biodiversity changes and could inform conservation efforts and regulatory interventions to protect biodiversity from pollution.

1 | Introduction

In the last three decades, global biodiversity has declined at an unprecedented pace, driven by climate change, habitat fragmentation and chemical pollution (Dirzo et al. 2014; Naggs 2017). This rapid loss of biodiversity has been linked to the decline of more than 60% of ecosystem services, including clean water, food provision and climate regulation (Ruckelshaus et al. 2020).

Freshwater ecosystems are among the most threatened by environmental change globally, having experienced a 83% biodiversity loss since 1970 (Acreman et al. 2020). This is likely because freshwater ecosystems are a commodity for many stakeholders, increasing the challenges to balance ecological and economic priorities (Dudgeon et al. 2006; Eastwood et al. 2022). In particular, freshwater lakes are widely exploited but not usually a target of conservation actions (Ahmed et al. 2022), even

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though their landscape position as ‘receivers’ of land-use effluents makes them more vulnerable to anthropogenic impact (Dudgeon et al. 2006). Understanding the status of biodiversity in these ecosystems is critical to assess their health and to design conservation plans.

Traditionally, biodiversity monitoring has been based on direct observations, remote sensing and mark recapture techniques (Eveleigh et al. 2007). While these approaches have provided important insights into species ecology and persistence in the face of environmental change, they have critical limitations. Cryptic diversity cannot be resolved through morphological observations; life stages of the same species with different morphology can be incorrectly classified; species assignment relies on visible remains in environmental matrices; species assignment requires specialist taxonomic skills; and the monitoring of biodiversity at scale is low throughput (Gillson and Marchant 2014). Indicator species are often used as surrogates of overall biodiversity to establish the ecological status of freshwater ecosystems, even though they are poor representatives of ecosystem-level change. Moreover, the drivers of biodiversity loss are not concurrently captured with biodiversity in monitoring efforts (Birk et al. 2012).

In the last decade, DNA-based methods have become more prominent for large-scale biodiversity monitoring (Balint, Nowak, et al. 2018), enabling a shift from morphological approaches (Bennion et al. 2011; Kelly et al. 2020; Zimmermann et al. 2014). The main advantages of these methods are their high throughput and cost-effectiveness, enabling the screening of biodiversity at different scales from any environmental matrix without the need for well-preserved remains (Cristescu and Hebert 2018). Also advantageous is the non-invasive nature of these methods and the opportunity to resolve cryptic genetic diversity by matching sequence similarity to records in public databases (e.g., NCBI and SILVA) (Taberlet et al. 2018), even though well-documented DNA baselines linked to vouchered specimens are patchier for tropical and polar species than they are for temperate species (Elias-Gutierrez and Valdez-Moreno 2023). DNA-based approaches have been used to estimate human impact on biodiversity (Hofman et al. 2015), the severity of alien species invasion (Ruppert, Kline, and Md Rahman 2019) and more generally species richness and distribution on the landscape (Garlapati et al. 2019). Yet, they have not been routinely applied to identify drivers of biodiversity loss; an exception being the case study by Eastwood et al. that aligns long-term trends in biodiversity and environmental change (Eastwood et al. 2023).

Land use, climate, topography, chemical pollution, typology, and physico-chemical changes play a crucial role in shaping the structure and diversity of freshwater aquatic communities. These drivers influence both the abiotic environment (e.g., water temperature, nutrient levels, flow regimes, and chemical concentrations) and biotic interactions (e.g., competition and predation). Changes in land use, such as agricultural expansion, can lead to habitat fragmentation, altered nutrient inputs and elevated levels of chemical pollutants such as pesticides, heavy metals, and pharmaceuticals, all of which have been shown to alter species composition and community dynamics in freshwater (Allan 2004; Jeppesen et al. 2011). Chemical pollution can directly affect the physiology and survival of sensitive species and

indirectly alter community structure by modifying predator-prey relationships and competitive interactions (Michelangeli et al. 2022). Climate change, especially the increased recurrence of extreme events such as floods and heat waves can alter hydrological patterns, influencing the availability and quality of habitats, as well as the physico-chemical parameters of water bodies (e.g., pH, dissolved oxygen, and turbidity), influencing survival and fitness of aquatic species (Adrian et al. 2009; Heino, Virkkala, and Toivonen 2009). The typology of freshwater habitats, such as depth and size of the water bodies, as well as altitude, influence fundamental ecological processes, such as species richness and community assembly. Together, these landscape-scale drivers create a complex mosaic of environmental conditions and ecological processes that govern the distribution, abundance, and diversity of freshwater communities across spatial and temporal scales. However, most studies investigating the causes of biodiversity loss focus on single environmental factors (Kambach et al. 2023) or use regression models that assume linear correlation between taxa and factors (MacNally 2000). Conversely, data-driven modeling (DDM), in particular multi-view learning and explainable machine learning are promising alternatives to handle complex, heterogeneous and non-replicated data, such as community biodiversity and multiple environmental factors or complex drivers such as climate change and pollution (Willcock et al. 2018). In particular, the fusion of interpretable models with multi-view learning frameworks allows the simultaneous interrogation of different data matrices and to discover non-linear correlations within (e.g., environmental variables), and between matrices (Li, Yang, and Zhang 2019). This approach was successfully used in a recent study investigating the impact of human activities on a lake community diversity (Eastwood et al. 2023). Moving from eDNA single-marker to multi-markers (Bohmann et al. 2022; Eastwood et al. 2023), and adopting machine learning algorithms to study complex interactions between biodiversity and complex environmental drivers comprising multiple factors, is a promising approach to explore ecosystem-level processes and community response to environmental change e.g., (Balint, Pfenninger, et al. 2018; Eastwood et al. 2023).

Here, we apply a recently developed metabarcoding multiplex approach (Eastwood et al. 2024) to study community biodiversity dynamics of pelagic and benthic freshwater communities from 52 lakes across England. We apply an explainable multi-modal machine learning pipeline that can integrate different data types, such as biological, chemical, and physical parameters, to discover the likely drivers of biodiversity dynamics. The machine learning approach is modified from a previous longitudinal study (Eastwood et al. 2023) to identify environmental drivers that influence the structure, composition, and functioning of freshwater ecosystems at national scale in England. The environmental drivers considered in this study were plant protection products obtained from national surveys, typology collected by the UK Centre of Ecology and Hydrology along with water quality indicators collected by the Environment Agency of England. Our data-driven approach revealed the likely drivers of biodiversity dynamics and the factors within these drivers that in isolation or in combination affected prokaryotic and eukaryotic relative abundance and their interactions. Our data-driven approach allows us to capture both drivers of community biodiversity change, as well as specific environmental factors

that explain changes in relative abundance of specific taxa within the community. By capturing both drivers and specific factors, our approach provides tangible targets for regulators to validate the putative causes of biodiversity loss as well as a holistic understanding of community biodiversity dynamics at landscape level.

2 | Methods

2.1 | Study System

A total of 52 freshwater English lakes were included in this study; biofilm and water samples were collected from these lakes by the Environment Agency of England (Figure S1). Water samples were from 40 lakes and biofilm samples from 42 lakes (Figure S1; Table S1). Hence, water and biofilm samples were concurrently sampled from 30 lakes (58% of lakes), allowing a synchronous analysis of benthic and pelagic communities. The lakes span lowland to high altitude and differ in catchment geology (Table S1).

Water samples were collected as part of a wider research program funded by the UK government between March 2017 and November 2019 (Table S1) following the UKTAG Environmental Standards, aimed at assessing vertebrate communities with eDNA (Hanfling et al. 2016; Willby et al. 2020). In brief, 2L of lake water was collected from 20 evenly spaced shoreline locations around the perimeter of each sampled lake. Each 2L sample comprised of 5 × 400 mL pooled subsamples taken at 5 m intervals away from inflow hotspots (Hanfling et al. 2016). Within 24 h of collection, samples were filtered on 47 mm diameter Whatman mixed cellulose ester membrane (Whatman, GE Healthcare, UK) on Nalgene filtration units (pore size 0.45 µm). Genomic DNA was extracted from the filtered water samples using the Mu-DNA Water protocol (Sellers et al. 2018). gDNA water extracts were stored at −20°C until further processing.

Biofilm samples were collected during a routine surveillance monitoring program by the Environment Agency of England between 2014 and 2016 (September–November; Table S1) to develop a metabarcoding method for diatom assessment in freshwater (Kelly et al. 2018, 2020). Briefly, five cobbles were placed in a tray with approximately 50 mL of lake water and brushed with a toothbrush to remove the biofilm. 5 mL of biofilm suspension was transferred to a sterile 15 mL centrifuge tube containing 5 mL nucleic acid preservative (3.5 M ammonium sulfate, 17 mM sodium citrate and 13 mM EDTA) and stored in cold conditions (ca. −20°C) for up to 8 years, before being used in this study. Genomic DNA was extracted using DNeasy power biofilm kit (Qiagen), following the manufacturer's instructions, with an extended overnight lysis.

2.2 | Community-Level Biodiversity

We quantified the pelagic and benthic communities from the 52 lakes, including prokaryotes and eukaryotes, by applying a recently developed 2-step metabarcoding PCR protocol (Eastwood et al. 2024). This protocol consists of a PCR1 multiplex including four gene makers and pooling and sequencing of up to 1536

samples (384 samples per gene marker) at the PCR2 step. The metabarcoding loci used in the multiplex were: two regions targeting eukaryotes broadly [(18SV1V2) (Hadziavdic et al. 2014) and (18SV8V9) (Bradley, Pinto, and Guest 2016)], and prokaryotes (16SV4) (Caporaso et al. 2011), plus a taxon-specific gene marker targeting diatoms (rbcL) (Kelly et al. 2018). Each biological sample was run in duplicate and handled as an independent sample in the downstream analysis (see below). Water samples (pelagic) included field blanks (molecular grade water transported alongside the water samples), which were pooled in equal volume aliquots (5 µL of extract) for each lake creating a reference 'field blank pool'. There were no equivalent field blanks for the biofilm (benthic) samples.

Each sample was amplified in triplicate in PCR1 using Q5 HS High-Fidelity Master Mix (New England Biolabs) following the manufacturer's instructions. After removing excess primers with High Prep PCR magnetic beads (Auto Q Biosciences), cleaned PCR1 products were pooled in PCR2 in which unique dual indexes pooling of up to 384 samples per barcode in a single sequencing run ($N = 1536$ samples per run). Unique dual barcodes were used to reduce index-misassignment and index-hopping between samples (MacConaill et al. 2018). Library construction blanks, consisting of PCR reactions without template DNA were used for both the biofilm and water DNA libraries. PCR2 amplified products were purified using High Prep PCR magnetic beads (Auto Q Biosciences) and quantitated using a 200 pro plate reader (TECAN) using qubit dsDNA HS solution (Invitrogen). A standard curve was created by running standards of known concentration on each plate against which sample concentration was determined. PCR2 libraries were mixed in equimolar quantities (at a final concentration of 12 pmol) using a biomek FXp liquid handling robot (Beckman Coulter). The final molarity of the pools was confirmed using a HS D1000 tapestation screentape (Agilent) prior to 250 bp paired-end sequencing on an DNBSec G400 following the conversion of linear dsDNA into circularized libraries compatible with the DNBSec platform using the MGIEasy Universal Library Conversion Kit.

2.3 | Environmental Drivers

A suite of environmental drivers was collected and consisted of plant protection products (PPP) survey data, typology and physico-chemical parameters. The PPP survey data were obtained from national surveys conducted by FERA Science Ltd. (formerly Food and Environment Research Agency) as part of a national program started in 1987 (<https://pusstats.fera.co.uk/data>). They were provided for five regions corresponding to five historical Ministry of Agriculture Fishing and Food regions across England: Northern (N), Eastern (E), South Eastern (SE), South Western (SW), Midlands & Western (M&W). A finer resolution than regional level was not possible to protect the privacy of farmers and landowners. For this study, we used the surveyed weight of active ingredients applied per year per region. The lakes used in this study were part of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) monitoring program (DEFRA 2014), under which a number of physico-chemical parameters are measured monthly by the Environment Agency of England. The mean value across the 3 months preceding the collection of water and biofilm samples was used when these parameters were present

in at least 50% of the lakes and had non-zero variance across sites—36 and 35 parameters were retained for water and biofilm samples, respectively (Table S4). This time interval was chosen over a yearly average to better align biodiversity responses to seasonal changes in physico-chemical parameters. Finally, typology (alkalinity, depth, size and altitude) were obtained from the ‘UK Lakes Portal’ (Hughes et al. 2004) (Table S5).

2.4 | Bioinformatics

The sequenced reads obtained from the metabarcoding of water and biofilm samples were demultiplexed using cutadapt v4.1 (Kambach et al. 2023), and analyzed with QIIME2 v2022.8 (Bolyen et al. 2019). Trimming, filtering, merging and denoising of reads was done using the QIIME2 DADA2 module (Callahan et al. 2016) with default parameters and trimming and truncation lengths as in Table S3. We first performed an exploratory analysis that included both water and biofilm samples in which all denoised reads were rarefied at the same depth of sequencing for comparative purposes; either the lowest read depth across the whole dataset or 1000 reads were used, whichever was higher. PCoA plots of beta diversity were obtained using weighted unifracs distance in QIIME2 and plotted in ggplot v3.4.0 (Wickham 2016) in R v4.0.2 (R Core Team 2020). This exploratory analysis revealed a clear separation between the biofilm and the water samples, hence, the two sample types were analyzed separately downstream (Figure S2).

Having established that the biofilm and water samples were to be analyzed separately, we repeated the rarefaction of the two sample sets on denoised reads to the sample with the lowest read depth within the sample type (water or biofilm). If the number of reads in this sample was less than the number of unique ASVs or amplicon sequence variants found in the locus, rarefaction was performed at a depth which retained 85% of samples. Diversity indices were measured on the rarefied reads separately for water and biofilm samples and calculated using the QIIME2 Diversity module. Alpha diversity was measured as Shannon diversity and Pielou evenness and plotted per lake and region. Differences in alpha diversity between regions were tested with Kruskal Wallis and pairwise Kruskal Wallis with Benjamini and Hochberg correction using alpha-group-significance in the QIIME2 diversity module. Beta diversity was quantified as weighted unifracs distance. We performed taxonomy assignment using default parameters (confidence value 0.7) with the QIIME2 feature-classifier module with naive-bayes taxonomic classifiers trained on the SILVA v138 database for the assignment of the 16S and 18S reads (Yilmaz et al. 2014); and the diat.barcode v11.1 for the rbcL reads (Rimet et al. 2019). The taxonomic assignment was visualized through barplots per geographic region, which included multiple lakes. These plots were generated using the rarefied reads with ggplot2 v3.4.0 (Caporaso et al. 2011) in R v4.0.2 (Eastwood et al. 2023; R Core Team 2020) and included the top ten most abundant genera. When classification was not possible at genus level, the lowest classification possible was used. All other taxa were collapsed in the plots under ‘other taxa’. The taxonomic classification per region was supported by a PERMANOVA test (999 permutations) applying the diversity adonis statistical test in QIIME2 and contrasting the biodiversity variance across the Ministry of Agriculture Fishing and Food regions.

2.5 | Linking Community-Level Biodiversity to Environmental Drivers

The water and biofilm community-level biodiversity were correlated with PPP survey data, physico-chemical parameters and typology properties to identify the putative drivers of landscape biodiversity dynamics.

All data were pre-processed to reduce noise and remove low quality data before downstream analyses. Preprocessing steps included the identification of outliers likely resulting from technical errors and the removal of features with more than 50% missing values. High number of missing values for certain parameters was due to the data collection criteria used. For example, certain chemicals are only measured in lakes so-called ‘of concern’, where different landscape pressures are associated with the lake. Consequently, these data are sporadic, inconsistent over time and only available for certain sites. Further preprocessing involved removing features with zero variance to eliminate non-informative features and applying collinearity detection to remove redundant features and mitigate multicollinearity. Through these methods, we removed variables that were uninformative, such as PPP below detection limits. Missing values were imputed using approaches suitable to the type of data. PPP survey data and physico-chemical parameters were imputed using the Akima interpolation method, which is most suitable for both spatial and temporal data (Akima 1970; Le Pichon et al. 2020). The remaining missing values were imputed using the k -Nearest Neighbors imputation method using $k=5$ as a minimum value window (Troyanskaya et al. 2001). Finally, a centered log-ratio (CLR) transformation was applied to normalize the denoised ASV matrices (Aitchison 1982; Liddicoat et al. 2022).

To establish correlations between biodiversity measured with ASVs and environmental drivers—PPP, physico-chemical parameters and typology—we modified the pipeline used in Eastwood et al. (2023) on a single lake ecosystem over time. As in the Eastwood et al. (2023), the input matrices in our study were ASVs and environmental drivers (PPP survey data, physico-chemical parameters and typology; Figure S5). We then applied a sparse Generalized Canonical Correlation Analysis (SGCCA) to correlate the ASVs with either of the three drivers. SGCCA is a powerful statistical method that extends traditional CCA for integrative analysis of more than two input datasets. SGCCA is preferred in our study because it not only focuses on the strongest relationships between the most informative and relevant variables across multiple datasets but also improves the model’s robustness by reducing noise and overfitting, which can impact traditional multivariate statistical approaches, enabling more reliable and interpretable insights into the drivers of biodiversity dynamics. Cross-validation was used to further reduce the risk of model overfitting and enhancing generalization. Specifically, we employed an optimisation algorithm, NSGA-II (Deb et al. 2002), to choose the sparsity parameters for SGCCA, and maximizing the variance captured within (e.g., taxa) and between input matrices (e.g., taxa and environmental factors). This ensures that the model identifies the most informative structure in the data. The optimized sparsity parameters were applied to support the identification of the most important factors within

the environmental drivers. Significantly correlated ASVs with abiotic factors were identified using 5000 runs of 10-fold cross-validation SGCCA to which a binomial test was applied to define an FDR-adjusted p -value < 0.05 .

In Eastwood et al. (2023), a Sliding Window Correlation (SWC) analysis was applied after the SGCCA step to find temporal correlations between biodiversity and abiotic factors. In our spatial survey, we ranked the factors within each driver according to their loading values, which indicate the contribution of each factor to the covariance captured by the SGCCA (Figure S5). We summarized the ASVs' loading values to the genus level and identified genera that significantly co-varied with top-ranked environmental factors, where loading values were significantly larger than randomly expected, following a permutation test with an FDR-adjusted p -value < 0.05 (5000 permutations). Significant correlations between genera and factors were identified as those with a Pearson correlation coefficient larger than 0.5, indicating large effect size, and an FDR-adjusted p -value < 0.05 following 5000 permutations.

3 | Results

3.1 | Community-Level Biodiversity

In five biofilm samples, one of the two replicate samples failed denoising across all loci and were excluded from downstream analyses. All water samples passed the denoising step and were retained (Table S1). The biofilm and water samples were significantly distinct, as the PCoA analysis supported by a PERMANOVA test showed (Figure S2, Table S2). Therefore, they were kept separate in the downstream analysis. The rarefied number of reads for the water samples were as follows: 16SV4: 1729 reads; 18SV1: 18,131 reads; 18SV8: 17,201 reads; and rbcL: 2076 reads. The rarefied number of reads for biofilm samples were as follows: 16SV4: 1130 reads; 18SV1: 14,029 reads; 18SV8: 21,734 reads; and rbcL: 14,890 reads (Table S3).

Alpha diversity ranged between 0.04–0.92 (Pielou evenness); 0.15–9.16 (Shannon Diversity) for water samples and between 0.25–0.93 (Pielou evenness) and 1.45–7.91 (Shannon Diversity) for biofilm samples (Figure S3). Generally, the alpha diversity did not significantly differ between regions, with the only significant difference (p value < 0.05) found with the Pielou evenness in the rbcL gene marker for the biofilm samples (p value = 0.030). Post hoc analysis (pairwise kruskal-wallis) showed that the significant differences were driven by differences between the Northern and South West regions ($Padj = 0.03$).

The community composition (beta diversity) of the water samples significantly differed among regions across three of the loci (16SV4, 18SV1, 18SV8), while it was not significant for the rbcL locus, as the PERMANOVA analysis indicates (Table 1). Conversely, the biofilm samples differed significantly among regions only for the rbcL locus while they did not significantly differ for the other three loci (Table 1). The taxonomic barplots confirmed the PCoA analysis, showing distinct compositions of the water and biofilm communities across the five regions: Northern (N), Midlands & Western (M&W), Eastern (E), South Western (SW) and South Eastern (SE). (Figure 1). The taxonomic

TABLE 1 | Permutational analysis of variance.

Sample type	Gene marker	F.model	R ²	<i>p</i>
Water	16SV4 ($n = 70$)	2.58	0.14	0.004
	18SV1V2 ($n = 80$)	4.62	0.20	0.001
	18SV8V9 ($n = 80$)	2.90	0.13	0.002
	rbcL ($n = 70$)	2.18	0.12	0.072
Biofilm	16SV4 ($n = 67$)	0.82	0.05	0.732
	18SV1V2 ($n = 78$)	1.33	0.07	0.134
	18SV8V9 ($n = 78$)	1.13	0.06	0.252
	rbcL ($n = 70$)	1.50	0.085	0.036

Note: PERMANOVA on beta diversity (weighted unifracs distances) between regions Midlands & Western (M&W), Eastern (E), SouthWestern (SW) and South Eastern (SE), measures across found gene markers (18SV1V2; 18SV8V9; 16SV4 and rbcL) in biofilm and water. The test was carried out using QIIME diversity adonis. Significant p -values ($p < 0.05$) following 999 permutations are in bold.

barplots per lake are also included for completeness (Figure S4). The number of genera (or the highest possible taxonomic classification) shared between the sample types (biofilm and water) was highest at the 16S locus, whereas only a limited number of abundant taxa were shared between the water and the biofilm communities across the other loci (Figure 1). Biofilm and water prokaryotic communities shared 60% of the 10 most abundant taxa: CL500-3 (family: *Phycisphaeraceae*); *Rhodoferrax*; *Verrucomicrobiaceae*; *Flavobacterium*; *Comamonadaceae*; Hgcl clade (family: *Actinobacteria*), plus Chloroplast DNA (Figure 1; 16S). Biofilm and water eukaryotic communities shared two of the topmost abundant taxonomic groups (*Diplostraca* and *Chlorophyceae*; Figure 1; 18SV1V2 and 18SV8V9). Biofilm and water diatom communities shared two of the topmost abundant taxa: *Navicula*, and *Aulacoseira* (Figure 1; rbcL).

3.2 | Drivers of Biodiversity Dynamics

Environmental drivers plant protection products [PPPs], physico-chemical parameters and typology explained a different proportion of biodiversity in water (Figure 2A) and biofilm samples (Figure 2B). A large proportion of the biodiversity variance in both samples was explained by typology and PPP, followed by physico-chemical parameters (Figure 2). Up to 38% of the water prokaryotic diversity was explained by PPPs, contributing to explain up to 97% of this diversity, and physico-chemical parameters, contributing 61% (Figure 2). As for the prokaryotic diversity, PPPs (98%) and physico-chemical parameters (63%) contributed to explain up to 28% of the water eukaryotic biodiversity (averaged between 18SV1 and 18SV8). Up to 54% of the water diatom community diversity was explained by PPPs (98%) and physico-chemical parameters (66%).

The explained benthic community diversity was lower than the pelagic diversity (Figure 2). The contribution of PPPs to the compositional changes across the loci was lower than in the benthic

FIGURE 1 | Legend on next page.

FIGURE 1 | Taxonomic bar plots including the top 10 most abundant genera (or the lowest classification possible) identified across four loci: 16SV4; 18SV1V2; 18SV8V9 and *rbcL* for water (A) and biofilm (B) samples. The lakes are grouped in five regions corresponding to Midlands & Western (M&W), Eastern (E), SouthWestern (SW) and South Eastern (SE). The color palette does not represent the same taxonomic group across plots or between sample types, but arranges the taxa from most (blue) to least abundant (red). Taxonomic barplots per lake are in Figure S5.

FIGURE 2 | Proportion of pelagic (A) and benthic (B) community biodiversity explained by environmental drivers: Plant protection products (PPP), typology, and physico-chemical parameters across four loci (16SV4; 18SV1V2; 18SV8V9 and *rbcL*). Percentages represent cumulative contributions of the first four sCCA components.

community and ranged between 87% for 16S and 90% for *rbcL* (Figure 2). Conversely, the contribution of physico-chemical parameters to the benthic biodiversity was higher, ranging between 66% in 18SV8 and *rbcL* and 67% in 18SV1 and 16S (Figure 2). Typology contributed equally to water and biofilm diversity with all four factors within this driver correlating with biodiversity across the marker genes. Given these patterns, the typology was less informative for explaining the landscape biodiversity dynamics.

Within plant protection products, insecticides and herbicides were the strongest contributors (highest loadings) to water biodiversity variance (Figure 3). This pattern was clear from insecticides being on the first and/or second component of the SGCCA plots (Figure 3). Insecticides and herbicides correlated with all biodiversity across the four loci, while fungicides correlated mainly with prokaryotes (Figure 3; 16SV4) and occasionally eukaryotes (Figure 3; 18SV1V2). Herbicides and fungicides across the loci contributed the most to biofilm biodiversity, as evident from the high loadings of these PPP across the loci (Figure 3).

Individual factors within typology all played a role on biodiversity across the gene markers in both water and biofilm diversity (Figure 3). However, alkalinity was always found on the first component across the loci in both biofilm and water samples (Figure 3). Forty-three physico-chemical factors contributed to drive biodiversity (Figure 3). Whereas it was difficult to identify

clear patterns for these factors, focusing on the first component, a different combination of physico-chemical factors affected biodiversity in water and biofilm (Figure 3).

A total of 29 water prokaryotic genera correlated with 59 PPPs, and four of these genera also correlated with three physico-chemical parameters (alkalinity, calcium and conductivity) (Figure 4; 16S). Four biofilm prokaryotic genera correlated with 34 PPPs, 12 of these PPPs and one of the genera were shared with the water prokaryotic community (Figure 4; 16S). Twenty-one water eukaryotic genera and one biofilm genus correlated with a suite of 7 physico-chemical parameters, whereas 51 PPPs correlated with Diptera in the biofilm eukaryotic community (Figure 4; 18S). Finally, the diatom *Nitzschia* dominated the *rbcL* locus, correlating with 57 PPPs in the biofilm community. In the water community, *Nitzschia* correlated with ammoniacal nitrogen and three PPPs, one of which (Diflufenican) was also identified within the biofilm community (Figure 4; *rbcL*).

4 | Discussion

Current environmental management is often ineffective, as monitoring programs typically focus on a few indicator species and easily measured environmental factors (e.g., temperature), overlooking the complex interaction between biodiversity and environmental change. This narrow approach, once adequate under regulations like the Water Framework Directive in 2000,

FIGURE 3 | Physico-chemical parameters, typology factors and chemical classes within plant protection products (PPP) significantly enriched in biofilm (open circles) and water (filled circles) samples across the four gene markers used in this study (16SV4; 18SV1V2; 18SV8V9 and rbcL) (Fisher's exact test; $p < 0.05$), as identified by the first four component of the SGCCA analysis.

is now insufficient to address the complexities of a world facing multiple stressors and rapidly emerging threats to water and wildlife. Effective conservation requires understanding of how factors within main drivers influence different taxonomic groups across various spatial scales, from regional to global, to identify the causes of biodiversity loss (Eastwood et al. 2022; Reid et al. 2019).

Our community-level survey of freshwater lakes at national scale, encompassing prokaryotes and eukaryotes, revealed that whereas pelagic communities significantly differed among regions and sites, the biofilm community did not, as the PERMANOVA analysis shows. Even though the quality of our biofilm samples is expected to be lower due to suboptimal

storage conditions, our results reflect patterns previously observed for biofilm and pelagic freshwater communities, namely non-significant difference among biofilms across freshwater ecosystems, significantly different community composition between pelagic and biofilm communities, and a landscape structure among pelagic communities (Besemer et al. 2012). Confidence in our data is provided by a comparable alpha diversity across locations in the biofilm samples. If storage affected the quality of samples, the overall diversity, measured as Shannon entropy and Pielou index, would vary randomly across the lakes and would have been significantly lower in the biofilm than the pelagic samples, whereas alpha diversity is generally comparable between sample types and occasionally higher in the biofilm samples.

FIGURE 4 | Sankey diagram showing significant links between genera identified by the four gene markers (18SV1V2 and 18SV8V9 are combined) in water and biofilm and factors within drivers (plant protection products [PPP] and physico-chemical parameters, no significant typology factors). Significant links are supported by a Pearson's correlation coefficient larger than 0.5 and an FDR-adjusted p -value < 0.05 following 5000 permutations. Left flow (factor) color indicates PPP group or physicochemical parameter, central flow (sample type and driver) color indicates sample type and all right flow (genera) are uncoloured.

Past studies have shown lower diversity in biofilm than pelagic biodiversity; however, these studies tend to focus on individual river ecosystems and on specific taxonomic groups (e.g., bacteria), (Niederdorfer, Peter, and Battin 2016), with few examples spanning multiple river ecosystems (Gweon et al. 2021). While these studies provide important insights into biodiversity dynamics at local scale, their scope is limited to illuminate large scale biodiversity dynamics. Our study provides one of the most comprehensive spatial assessments of freshwater benthic and pelagic communities encompassing prokaryotes and eukaryotes at different spatial scales—individual lake, regional and national scale. Our survey contributes to a granular mapping of freshwater biodiversity, improving the understanding of freshwater dynamics at different spatial scales. Surveys of community-level biodiversity, such as the one presented here, can contribute to the mapping of biodiversity through global initiatives e.g., the Global Biodiversity Information Facility, an open platform for crowd-sourced species observations (<https://www.gbif.org/>).

Different composition and diversity of pelagic and biofilm communities can be explained by colonization and establishment mechanisms. Two major processes are known to influence how communities are assembled: neutrality-based stochastic and niche-based deterministic processes (Lindstrom and Langenheder 2012; Soininen, Heino, and Wang 2018; Vellend 2010). In the former process, communities are randomly assembled and subject to ecological drift; in the latter process, community assemblage is determined by biotic (e.g., competition) and abiotic (e.g., nitrogen availability in the system) filtering. Evidence suggests that the relative influence

of deterministic processes in community dynamics are much higher in benthic than planktonic habitats where stochastic processes play a more significant role (Gweon et al. 2021). However, to date these colonization processes have not been considered in presence of disturbance caused by environmental drivers. For instance, chemical pollution has never been included in the modeling of these mechanisms. Resilience to environmental threats may strongly influence the overall diversity and composition of the communities (e.g., Mah and O'Toole 2001), therefore is it intuitive that it may also influence the colonization mechanisms of communities. Not accounting for these threats can lead to incorrect estimates of colonization mechanisms. Only by coupling biodiversity with environmental drivers and water quality parameters, we can begin to understand the real causes of biodiversity dynamics and loss. Our approach enables a better understanding of how human-driven changes can disturb establishment mechanisms of freshwater communities.

Emerging efforts like life mapper (Cavner et al. 2014) and Aquamaps (<https://www.aquamaps.org/>) are informative for the development of species distribution maps. However, they are still coarse and do not include links to environmental drivers, preventing us from understanding what causes biodiversity loss. Our data-driven approach allowed us to understand not only the biodiversity composition of the benthic and pelagic communities but also to identify potential drivers of biodiversity dynamics at different spatial scales. We were able to identify both general patterns of covariation between overall biodiversity and environmental drivers and the factors within drivers correlating with specific genera. Whereas these correlations

do not prove causation, they unveil ecosystem-wide response, reducing the intricate nature of natural systems into testable hypotheses that can be empirically verified in controlled laboratory settings, without the need to set preconceived hypotheses, which may be reductive or biased (Eastwood et al. 2022). It also provides testable hypotheses for modeling exercises studying establishment mechanisms of freshwater communities.

Our results show that insecticides and herbicides within PPPs were the strongest contributors to water biodiversity dynamics and explained up to 53.6% of biodiversity compositional changes across the landscape. Biofilm biodiversity was also strongly influenced by herbicides, with fungicides coming up second. PPPs explained up to 28% of the compositional changes of the benthic community biodiversity. These findings are aligned with previous discoveries on a freshwater lake sampled across 100 years and studied using a data-driven machine learning approach like the one adopted here (Eastwood et al. 2023). Our findings align with projections of biodiversity scenarios suggesting that land-use is the driver with the largest global impact on biodiversity by the year 2100 (Sala et al. 2000). Land-use is projected to have a larger impact on freshwater ecosystems, especially lakes, because human establishments are, and historically have been, higher near waterways. The higher population density around waterways increases habitat degradation and overuse of resources. Moreover, human establishments use waterways for discharge of effluents from domestic and industrial processes, increasing chemical pollutants and nutrients input in freshwater ecosystems (Sala et al. 2000).

While chemical pollution is the strongest contributor to biodiversity dynamics, both our study and others showed the significant role played by other environmental drivers in shaping landscape biodiversity. In our study, typology and physico-chemical parameters contributed to overall biodiversity compositional changes in both water and biofilm. Typology is commonly used to partition spatial variability, and ultimately gauge anthropogenic effects on biodiversity loss. For example, fish diversity has been positively correlated with freshwater lake size and inversely correlated with altitude (Volta et al. 2011). Alkalinity, the factor predominantly correlated with overall biodiversity in our study, has been previously linked to species richness (Declerck et al. 2006; Jeppesen, Søndergaard, Jensen, et al. 2005; Vestergaard and Sand-Jensen 2000). However, although typology is a key part of European legislation to assess water quality status of freshwater ecosystems (European Union 2000), its links to species richness and assemblages are inconclusive (Angeler and Johnson 2012). Confirming previous findings, typology contributed to explain overall biodiversity patterns in our study but was equally important in biofilm and water communities. Moreover, none of the typology factors could be directly linked to specific genera significantly responding to environmental change (discussed below), suggesting that these factors are non-discriminant to specific genera distributional patterns and to community type (e.g., benthic versus pelagic communities).

The influence of physico-chemical parameters on biodiversity is more robustly documented across several indicator species than typology. Physico-chemical parameters are more widely studied because they have been routinely used within regulatory frameworks (e.g., Water Framework Directive) to assess water quality.

Typically, the parameters contributing to changes in biodiversity are temperature, pH, conductivity, dissolved oxygen and nutrients, in addition to heavy metals. The most studied genera for their association with these parameters are primary producers, zooplankton and microbes e.g., (Pavic et al. 2023). Our results confirm the relevance of the physico-chemical parameters identified in previous studies and used in regulatory frameworks, indicating that nutrients, pH, and heavy metals all contribute to community biodiversity dynamics.

Whereas our study showed that different drivers may contribute to biodiversity dynamics, a good proportion of the biodiversity variance remained unexplained. This is expected as important factors such as eutrophication and climate change were not included in our study. Including more drivers would have likely improved our understanding of biodiversity compositional change and provided a better understanding of potential drivers of biodiversity dynamics. However, this approach was not possible because only a proportion of potential drivers was sampled across all lakes. It is common practice in monitoring programs to perform asynchronous sampling of biodiversity and environmental factors and to inconsistently sample across space and time, except for a few parameters. A more consistent sampling over space and time of both biodiversity and environmental factors can help pinpoint the causes of biodiversity loss.

Our data-driven systemic approach enabled us not only to discover putative drivers of biodiversity dynamics, but also pinpoint the abiotic factors within these drivers (PPP, physico-chemical parameters and typology) correlating with prokaryotic and eukaryotic genera. This analysis revealed a total of 99 active substances, present in herbicides, insecticides, molluscicides, fungicides and growth regulators, affected the relative abundance of 34 genera. Genera significantly correlating with these active substances included many non-target genera, such as primary producers, invertebrate larvae, and numerous bacteria. These organisms are instrumental to ecosystem functions, such as nitrification/denitrification, photosynthesis, and nutrient turnover. Additionally, they are near impossible to identify using conventional survey methods such as morphological identification. Not surprisingly their abundance was significantly correlated also to physico-chemical properties, such as carbon, nitrogen, and calcium.

When we drilled into the specific active substances that correlated with the prokaryotic and eukaryotic genera, we identified substances with documented adverse effects, which serve to benchmark our data-driven approach, discovering known threats to biodiversity. We identified two substances that are currently banned by the European Commission to correlate significantly with non-target genera: Diquat (herbicide) and Chlorothalonil (fungicide) (Lewis et al. 2016). Diquat is an endocrine disruptor highly soluble in water and very persistent in soil, banned by the European Union in 2019 for demonstrated adverse effects on human health (Fortenberry et al. 2016). We found it to significantly correlate with Diptera, likely larval stages common in aquatic ecosystems. In addition, we identified significant correlations with primary producers (*Nitzschia*) and several pelagic bacteria, including photosynthetic bacteria (e.g., *Acetobacteraceae*), and bacteria associated with water and gut microbiota (*Burkholderiales*). Chlorothalonil is a broad-spectrum fungicide. It tends not to be persistent in soil systems

but may be persistent in water (Lewis et al. 2016). It has been associated with cognitive impairment and low sperm quality in vertebrates (Guillante et al. 2024). Chlorothalonil was banned in 2019 in the EU and UK after it was found by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) to be a presumed carcinogen (Authority 2018). In our study it correlated with primary producers and Diptera. Our samples span the years 2014–2019, hence our findings do not necessarily suggest an improper use of these active substances in the UK. However, the link between freshwater genera and these substances clearly supports evidence of adverse effects on wildlife. Our results also open a new pathway to the identification of yet unknown active substances for their effects on wildlife without restrictions imposed by preconceived hypotheses, commonly adopted when studying indicator species.

Other examples of active substances correlating significantly with non-target species include the insecticide Deltamethrin. Significantly correlating with both prokaryotes and eukaryotes, Deltamethrin is a high-selling neurotoxic insecticide worldwide (Li et al. 2021). As a fast-acting insecticide, it is supposed to have a very targeted effect on invertebrates alone, but we found it to be significantly co-varying with many prokaryotes and a primary producer in addition to Diptera. These findings are in line with previous studies showing neurotoxic effect in freshwater fish, even at low doses (Strungaru et al. 2019) as well as phototoxic effect in primary producers (Kock et al. 2022).

The herbicide Glyphosate, also known as Roundup, has been at the core of numerous lawsuits for its putative link to cancer (Chang et al. 2023). In our study, it significantly co-varied with primary producers (*Nitzschia*) and many water bacteria, including photosynthetic bacteria (*Cyanobacteria*), free living bacteria (*Verrucomicrobia*) and bacteria common to the gastrointestinal tract of living organisms (*Bacteroidetes*). Our findings are supported by previous studies showing adverse effects of glyphosate on aquatic invertebrates and their microbiota (Suppa et al. 2020). The disruptive effect of herbicides on microbiota is worrying as the microbiota plays a pivotal role in maintaining organism and ecosystem's health. In addition to the potential effect of Glyphosate on microbiota, our study identified the herbicide Mesotrione as a potential cause of concern for biofilm bacteria playing a central role in nutrient cycling (*Planctomycetes*), endosymbionts (*Verrucomicrobiota*) and bacteria found in the gut microbiome of many species, including humans (*Burkholderiales*). The adverse effects of this active substance have been documented in freshwater algae (Moro et al. 2012) and fish (Wang, Harwood, and Zhang 2018). In summary, the data-driven approach identified known substances with adverse effects on wildlife and several unknown active substances that should be further investigated. The active components discussed here serve as prime illustrations, supported by prior research in aquatic environments and wildlife. A more exhaustive list of active substances and the genera co-varying with them is provided in this study for further explorations by both scientists and regulators.

Our data-driven, holistic approach is potentially transformative, facilitating ecosystem-level biodiversity monitoring and directing regulatory efforts toward scrutinizing active

components exhibiting adverse impacts on wildlife. The samples used in this study were somewhat opportunistic, having been sampled by regulators for routine screening of lake water quality as part of the Water Framework Directive monitoring program. However, they only reflect a single snapshot in time of patterns that may result from processes over time (Eastwood et al. 2022; Nogues-Bravo et al. 2018). Moreover, we did not include the effect of climate as a potential driver of biodiversity dynamics. Climate change, especially extreme temperature events have been shown to contribute to changes in biodiversity over time (Eastwood et al. 2023). The use of single time-points and the exclusion of climate as a potential driver may explain the proportion of biodiversity in our study that could not be linked to any of the studied drivers. More importantly, our results point to the enormous potential of sampling freshwater ecosystems through time to understand the cause-effect relationships between biodiversity dynamics and environmental drivers, as a previous proof of concept study suggests (Eastwood et al. 2023). The inclusion of as many drivers as possible and their combined effect over time can significantly advance our understanding of the causes of biodiversity loss. Our approach generates testable hypotheses that can be empirically verified in controlled laboratory settings, which are critical to establish causation between biodiversity loss and environmental drivers and factors but often unrealistic, given the number of factors potentially affecting biodiversity.

Author Contributions

N.E. performed eDNA metabarcoding data analysis. N.E. and A.W. completed data analysis and visualized machine learning outputs. J.Z. developed machine learning algorithms to link biodiversity to environmental factors. L.O. conceived the study and supervised data analysis. J.Z. and L.O. coordinated the study and supervised N.E. and A.W. All authors contributed to manuscript writing.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The metabarcoding sequences generated for this project are available at BioProject ID PRJNA1112619.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.